

APPROACHES TO ENSURING MORAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL STABILITY IN FOREIGN ARMIES

Mirashirova Nargiza Anvarovna

Doctor of Philosophy in Psychological Sciences (PhD),

Associate Professor (Uzbekistan)

E-mail: mirashirova72@mail.ru

Ashurmatov Muzaffar Komilovich

Senior researcher doctoral student of the doctoral Department
of the Academy of the Armed Forces, of the Republic of Uzbekistan (Uzbekistan)

E-mail: muzaffarashurmatov3@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13777323>

Annotation. This article scientifically and practically analyzes the moral and psychological state of military personnel, which is the main guarantee of victory in combat operations, and issues of ensuring its sustainability. Attention is paid to a group of moral, general psychological and individual psychological elements, as well as professional elements that make up the moral and psychological state. Also, based on the experience of leading foreign armies in terms of psychological training of military personnel, their achievements and shortcomings are discussed.

Key words: Armed forces, moral and psychological state, psychological stability, psychological characteristics, moral and psychological training, pragmatism, egocentrism, psychogenic losses, psychological support.

Introduction.

The analysis of recent political, economic and military events in the world shows that the military-political leadership of the world's leading countries demonstrates maintaining the high moral and spiritual status of the personnel of the armed forces as one of the priorities in the field of ensuring national security. According to military experts, factors that negatively affect the mental stability of military personnel are increasing in modern hostilities. A number of analysts agree that the outcome of a modern war depends on the mental state of the personnel, their ability to overcome their fear of battle while maintaining the will to win. Today it can be said with confidence that it is the mental state of military personnel that has become the main target of the enemy. An example of this is armed conflicts in the Middle East. It was observed that not only some of the informational-psychological effects were used, but they were all applied. Some researchers noted that this war marked the end of the era of classical warfare and the beginning of the era of electronic, information and other technologically based wars.

Materials and methods.

In the army of each state, the moral and spiritual support of military personnel is carried out differently. In this, the main attention is focused on ensuring the high moral and spiritual condition of military personnel and preparing them mentally and physically for combat situations.

The armies of the world do not have a single approach in this direction. For example, America, Great Britain, Germany, France and other Western countries call the training aimed at forming and developing the moral and spiritual qualities of military personnel in their armies with names such as "Political education", "Formation of fighting spirit", "Ethical training". Also, the concept of "Ethical-spiritual state" is interpreted as "Optimistic spirit", "The level of trust in the spirit and mind of a group, a person"[1].

Studying and evaluating the training system of military personnel in foreign armies has been of regular interest to military researchers.

According to analysis of of Russian military experts such as S. Zavyalov, P. Shitov, E. Chinukvadze, S. Vorontsov, V. Utkin and M. Zelenkov leading Western countries especially NATO members like the USA, Great Britain, Germany, and Turkey, have established institutional, organizational, economic and ideological-political systems to regulates the field [2;3].

These systems operate based on the objectives of the military alliance and the national interests of each country.

The USA system of psychological support in the army is structured as follows: the unit commander and a junior medical specialist identify persons with combat psychological injuries and provide them with initial emergency psychological support. Then they send the injured to medical centers. Here, for a few hours, they are provided with pre-medical psychological support (sleep, hot drinks, quality food, rest and the least amount of pharmacological drugs).

Maintaining a clear schedule and military uniform is a mandatory condition for mental health recovery. If a positive result is not achieved, the treatment is continued in a psychiatric care institution or in an inpatient hospital. According to experts, the effectiveness of such assistance is 55-75%. This scheme was tested during the Persian Gulf War [4].

The Great Britain personnel of the army is traditionally distinguished by high professionalism, psychological stability, physical endurance, the ability to perform combat operations at any time of the day, in harsh climates, familiarity with weapons, confidence in military strength, military, moral superiority and qualities.

The process of forming durable and high moral and spiritual qualities originates from the national psychological aspects of the British soldier. During the training process, special attention is paid to the development of such qualities as mental stability, coolness, businesslike use of situations, ability to adapt to any situation, effective use of strength and knowledge, perseverance, foresight, and military cunning.

To fulfill these tasks, the posts of psychiatrist and psychologist in the British Armed Forces have been introduced in each divisional headquarters. They closely monitor the process of moral-spiritual maintenance in military units and units and deal with the problems of morale strengthening of various categories of servicemen.

Germany military-political leadership pays special attention to maintaining the combat morale of military personnel at an appropriate level. In particular, the Bundeswehr has a multi-level system for creating a positive moral – spiritual environment. In particular, the uniqueness of national psychology is an integral element that provides the necessary moral – spiritual environment of the German Armed Forces.

The moral and spiritual state of Bundeswehr servicemen: stable faith in the power and capabilities of the state, a deep enough understanding of the reasons for military duty, heavy emotional stress, pragmatism¹, collectivity in service issues, egocentrism² in personal life, a sufficiently developed feelings defined by its compatibility with, initiative indicator and adherence to laws.

In the medical battalion of each division of the armed forces of Turkey, there are from three to six specialist assistants of psychiatrists, psychologists, sociologists appointed from among the ranks of sergeants, who monitor the correct implementation of moral and spiritual training in the unit.

In the armed forces of Germany and Greece, officers of special bodies with pedagogical and psychological training participate in the organization of activities in this field.

Result and discussion.

Raising of the moral mental state of the military personnel, who are involved in combat actions, has been researched for many years. According to military experts, the series of factors that affect the raising of the moral and mental state of personnel composition includes:

¹Pragmatism (Greek: pragmatos - work, action) is a philosophical doctrine that puts forward the idea that it is necessary to give more importance to what is most useful to a person in practice.

²Egocentrism (lat. ego - me and - center) is a characteristic of a person's attachment to his own sphere of interest, his view of other people and things in relation to his initial knowledge or his inability to change his mind, even to adapt to information that is contrary to his own experience.

the development of the military-industrial system of the state and the provision of power and the requirements of the modern military-political situation and the national security of the country;

use of science and technology for military purposes and further development of the country's military-industrial complex;

organization of moral - spiritual support activities covering all categories of servicemen organization of coverage; improvement of staff, army operational and combat training processes;

strengthening the social protection of military personnel and, most importantly, raising the material interest of the personnel; activities composition conducting aimed at increasing the professional-qualification level of military administration bodies.

As we know, the result of any training is evaluated by the tolerance of the military personnel to various influences on the battlefield and the completion of the assigned combat mission.

Military experts of leading foreign armies say that during combat operations, only 20-25 percent of soldiers independently perform the necessary actions (shooting at a target, purposeful movement on the battlefield, etc.), and the rest show activity only when they see the commander. Otherwise, they hide in a safe place, pretend to fail equipment, weapons, suffer mental and physical injuries in their actions, and also try to join the back of their wounded colleagues [5].

Based on the experience of armed conflicts and hostilities, in order to maintain a strong moral and spiritual state, the leaders of the alliance countries are widely using mass media as a means of positive influence on military personnel.

Also, currently, NATO countries have developed the program "Formation of moral and spiritual qualities of personnel in the 21st century" in the armies, which defines the main requirements for military personnel: high intelligence, physical strength and strong motivation for military service. The document has developed a practical mechanism for inculcating traditional moral-spiritual and moral-aesthetic standards, and this approach affects the spirit and mind of military personnel in a situation closely related to the principles of material incentives.

Based on the above, it can be concluded that the unique institutional foundations of the morale-spiritual support system in the studied leading foreign armies are explained by the presence of special apparatus in all units of

the Armed Forces, the branching and strict subordination of relevant bodies, and the possession of a high-quality legislative institution.

It is determined by the existence of the organizational foundations in harmony with the composition of highly qualified personnel, a comprehensive approach to solving the problem, the interdependence of education and training, the accuracy of practice and the planning of every step.

The economic foundations of moral and spiritual support are seen in the existence of a strong material and financial base at the disposal of management bodies, as well as the allocation of sufficient funds to the sector.

The existence of a well-defined ideological-theoretical and methodological basis and the use of the service of Chaplains (priests) by the military-political leadership, in the spirit of solidarity with the alliance in NATO, and in other Western countries based on the national interest of the state, to educate such qualities as patriotism, morality and national spirit is explained by its focus.

Conclusion.

Based on the above, the following are defined as the strengths of the moral and spiritual support of military personnel of the armed forces of foreign countries:

deep scientific and methodical development of forms and methods of creating spiritual and martial qualities;

availability of a good material and technical base for training soldiers and officers;

use of the achievements of science and technology in order to increase the effectiveness of the educational process;

creating ample opportunities for the direct organizers of personnel training.

In turn, the shortcomings in the moral and spiritual support of the personnel of these armies include:

increased mental pressure on the process of personnel training during combat operations in the conditions of modern warfare;

an increase in excessive enthusiasm for material incentives, which harms the moral education of the military;

the conflicting nature of individual arguments and theses used in academic work;

absence of a single responsible body for personnel training and etc.

References:

1. Обучение и воспитание военнослужащих в зарубежных армиях.
<http://www.podelise.ru/docs/index-25334746-1.html>

POLAND

CURRENT APPROACHES AND NEW RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCES

International scientific-online conference

POLAND

2. Э.Чинуквадзе. Новые тенденции в организации морально-психологической подготовки военнослужащих стран НАТО. Зарубежное военное обозрение. 2008. №3. С. 31-34.

3. Организация морально-психологической подготовки войск иностранных армий к ведению боевых действий. https://studbooks.net/1202360/bzhd/organizatsiya_moralno_psihologicheskoy_podgotovki_voysk_inostrannyh_armiy_vedeniyu_boevyh_deystviy.

4. Шитов А. Морально-психологические проблемы военнослужащих США. // Зарубежное военное обозрение. – 2013, № 9 С. 34-38.

5. А.Караян. Психологические особенности боевых действий военнослужащих в различных видах и на различных этапах боя. ArmyRus.ru. военно-информационный портал. http://armyrus.ru/index.php?option=com_content&task=view&id=742&Itemid=2156